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Wearable Sports Technologies

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Keywords

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ABSTRACT

Today, wearable monitoring systems created thanks to technological advances are integrated into the human body and are widely used in many fields from sports to health. These systems, in which multiple disciplines work together simultaneously, provide physiological and biochemical data, enabling the determination of the current situation and the creation of appropriate performance and improvement programs for individuals. In this review study, 23 articles, 4 of which were review articles, published in the Sports Sciences category on the Web of Science database in 2024 were examined using the keywords "wearable technology" and "sports". As a result of the review of these articles, it was determined that 8 articles were not related to the subject of wearable technologies in sports and were removed from the review (19 articles were included in the study). When studies on wearable technology in the field of sports sciences are examined, most studies are conducted on runners, and performance monitoring and injury prevention are among the main reasons for using this innovative technology. Considering the increasing technological developments, it is evaluated that the studies in this field will increase in parallel with this development and will make great contributions to the field of sports sciences.

1. INTRODUCTION

The role of technological products in sports, which exist in every aspect of our lives, has changed drastically with the developments in technology and digitalization. With the emergence of the internet and mobile technologies, technology has become indispensable for many sports [1].

Technology has contributed to playing sports potentially more exciting and challenging than ever before, playing a "vital role in being the best on and off the field" [2]. In these challenging conditions of high competition and performances that exceed human limits, the sports industry increasingly needs the use of technology to facilitate performance improvements [3].

Today, sport utilizes technology at the highest level, which has led to rapid advances in many sports [4]. However, technology has started to be used not only for performance improvement but also in the field of health to help individuals lead a healthier life and to understand the complex structure of the body. Collecting patient data with

technological devices also informs healthcare professionals and influences their treatment decisions [5].

Wearable devices, which can be used daily in both sports and health fields and can provide information flow with numerical data, show a rapidly growing trend in this technology network [6]. This study aims to examine the studies on wearable technologies in the field of sports sciences in 2024.

Wearable Technologies

Although there are different definitions of wearable technology in the literature [7], it is defined as "tools that are comfortable to use and wearable, portable, have sensors, and provide information transfer even when not in active use" [8]. Although it seems to be a concept of today, the beginning of wearable technological devices dates back to the 16th century. Watches hung around the

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neck like necklaces took their first place in history as pocket watches that individuals carried with them [9]. On the other hand, the first wearable device example in the literature was produced to benefit the user by cheating in the roulette game. A device placed on the sole of the shoe informed the user which number would come out thanks to the vibrations it sent to the person, thus benefiting the

user [10]. Today, wearable devices can be in many different forms such as watches, glasses, and wristbands [11]. These networked smart devices equipped with wireless communication capabilities [12] (Fig. 1.) can collect data, monitor activities, and customize experiences according to users' wishes and needs [13].

Figure 1. Block diagram example of a fitness wearable device process. [12]

When wearable devices work, there are 3 phases:

I. The first stage is sensors. Sensors are placed as close to the body as possible to monitor temperature, movement, and pulse.

II. The second stage is the connectivity and control part. Connecting via Bluetooth is the most widely used protocol for connecting wearable devices to a smartphone or home network.

III. The third phase is the data provision and reading of the wearable device [14].

The Place of Wearable Technology in Our Lives

Wearable technology products have now entered many areas of human life. Today, developing technology has accelerated the transition of societies from industrial society to information society. With this rapid transition, the contribution of wearable technological products, whose production and sales have increased, to the economy cannot be ignored. There is strong competition among wearable technologies, which have a wide market, and new features are added or completely renewed to the products produced daily. Companies' race to adapt to this changing and developing technology greatly affects the integration of wearable technology products in different sectors such as health, textiles, education,

entertainment, and tourism [15]. The wearable technologies market has become increasingly competitive with new products designed to provide consumers with access to more services. China is the largest market for wearables and the US is the second largest. The market is growing strongly as low-cost products and basic devices attract new users [16]. In this market race, sensors and microprocessors in devices can be integrated into garments to increase the functionality of sportswear, even at invisible dimensions [17].

Places of Use

Ergonomic and anthropometric positioning of wearable devices is crucial for success, regardless of the intended use (e.g., athlete performance improvement, health). Consumers need to know the movement limitations when wearing the device before purchasing [18]. Data shows that wrist devices are preferred for ease of use [12] (Fig. 2.). However, despite the rapid increase in the use of these smartwatches and wristbands, some functional difficulties can also be experienced due to sensitive skin on the wrist skin due to application sites, poor attachment problems due to displacement, and motion artifacts (sudden high-frequency activity) [19].

Figure 2. Worldwide wearable device shipments projected 2020

The main function of technological products used on the wrist among wearable devices is to monitor the basic characteristics of the body (such as heart rate, blood pressure, and concentration levels). These products make recommendations such as increasing the level of exercise or visiting a doctor [20]. Smart watches and wristbands (Figure 3.) have a wireless Bluetooth adapter that connects to a smartphone. With such devices, users can perform many actions such as answering phone calls, reading text messages and e-mails, analyzing physical activities, tracking fitness and health-related activities, and listening to music [21]. The use of these devices also dates to recent history. These devices are easy to use, compatible with many lifestyles, and allow tracking much more data than smartphones [22]. Apart from these popular body-worn devices (wrist), there are also modular equipment with embedded sensors or smart textiles [23]. The aim of these different approaches to wearable technology in sports is to enable users to track their performance in the best possible way without hindering any movement. This also depends on where the sensor is placed in the equipment, whether it is an accessory or not [24, 25]. In some sports, such as soccer, there is an external factor that affects biomechanical movements. Soccer shoes with sensors on the outsole are known to generate data showing the maneuvering characteristics of the ball (Figure 3.). It would be useful to monitor how the same sensors react when placed inside the shoe (insoles) (Figure 3.). Correlating this with precise biomechanical movements allows the user to maximize the understanding of their movements. The opportunity to self-learn different ways to

improve devices is a great function of human-centered design [26].

With the advances in technology, flexible sensors, conductive yarns, and materials with smartphone features have been developed and embedded in clothing [27, 28]. These devices can be used without the need to place them in any accessory as in modular use, and the clothing design itself has been made suitable for monitoring data [29]. A wearable product, referred to as a smart shirt, can measure important body variables such as heart rate, breath rate, heart rhythm patterns, calorie intake, sugar, and blood pressure (Figure 3.), record their values via a digital assistant, and notify with an audible warning system in case of a negative situation [30-32]. Similarly, smart socks (Figure 3.), a product called "Owlet", were developed for babies by Jacob Colvin, an academic at Brigham Young University, and enabled the monitoring of values such as heart rhythm and body temperature from smartphones [33].

Wearable technological devices are also involved in visual and auditory mechanisms. Like a minicomputer that contains images and sounds from the outside world, they have internal and external sensors that can collect data from computers, smartphones, and other electronic devices. Moreover, these devices have wireless connections that support GPS, Wi-Fi, and Bluetooth, allowing users to connect to the internet, watch videos and listen to audio. Some smart glasses also include facial recognition software, built-in cameras, GPS, and other applications[34].

Figure 3. Wearable technological products used in the field of Sports Sciences

Performance athletes and the use of wearable technology

Wearable technologies are now accepted and widely used in numerous sports and fitness activities across all performance levels, from recreational athletes to professionals, individual sports, and team sports, including non-disabled athletes [35]. Wearables can track athletes' performance (e.g., distance and speed) and the techniques they use to produce that performance (e.g., joint angles). The most common types of wearable devices available are typically wrist-worn smartwatches, chest straps, devices mounted on or inside shoes, or, more recently, devices built into sportswear [12]. Analysis of the data obtained with these devices can be used to measure subsequent fitness improvements, help reduce the risk of injury [36, 37], monitor recovery [38], monitor technique [39], or simply increase motivation at the user level [40]. Typical sensors used in wearable technologies are as follows:

- Inertial measurement units (e.g. accelerometers),
- Global positioning systems (GPS-based tracking devices)
- Heart rate sounders (electrocardiography, ECG)
- Muscle stimulation sensors (electromyography, EMG)

People with disabilities and the use of wearable technology

Today, wearable technologies lack accessibility for people with disabilities. However, considering the high accessibility in the laboratory stage, new developments in wearable technologies can be observed. When we look at some of these developments; a device called “Goby” [41], a swimming aid for visually impaired individuals, can prevent the athlete from going out of the lane and hitting the wall in turns by sending audio feedback with a camera placed on the body facing down in the water (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Goby is a wearable device that provides audio feedback for swimmers. Left: A swimmer wearing the Goby prototype in the pool. Right: Goby's wearable camera identifies and tracks a lane marker at the bottom of the pool [41].

Use of wearable technology in healthcare

Wearable technologies have been applied in exercise physiology, rehabilitation and other disciplines and have become a convenient tool for nurses and other healthcare professionals. These devices can provide information about important parameters related to the patient, such as location, heart and respiratory rate via GPS (Global Positioning System), and also have diagnostic applications that help in clinical decision-making [5].

Difficulties such as increasing health costs, shortage of personnel, inadequate health services in underdeveloped regions have accelerated the transition to new technology instead of traditional health services [42]. With wearable health products, patients can be monitored regularly and continuously, and patients and doctors can be informed about the stages of the disease. Smart health products store information such as the user's blood sugar, pulse, sweating, and blood pressure [15]. During the monitoring of these variables, systems that can notify in case of symptoms such as deterioration in heart rhythm,

loss of balance, low blood pressure, and even intervene in the first place have taken their place as important application areas in the field of health [43]. The benefits of wearable devices for clinical applications can be summarized as follows [44]:

- ✓ Ability to make and transmit simultaneous instant and accurate measurements,
- ✓ Patient follow-up in home environment
- ✓ Ensuring patient compliance and participation in treatment,
- ✓ Reducing costs that may arise from the need for clinics.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Screening and identification of articles

"Web of Science" search engine was utilized in this review study. The keywords "wearable technology" and "sport" were used for the search (Fig. 5.). The articles were identified as "sport science" (Fig. 6.) and "review" and "article" (Fig. 4.) and only studies conducted in 2024 were included.

Figure 5. Web of science index

Figure 6. Publication types

Figure 7. Number of publications by science fields

Figure 8. Number of publications by sport sciences

Figure 9. Number of publications in sports sciences by year

wearable technology in sports sciences, it is seen that performance tracking and analysis

2.2. Statistical Analysis

In our study, descriptive statistics method was used. In the review, data on the year, method and methodology, sample group, areas where wearable technologies are used and results of the studies were used.

3. Results

Initially, 2906 publications on wearable technologies were reached (Fig. 5.) and review scans (Fig. 4.) were performed. The distribution of studies according to countries is shown (Fig. 6.). In the field of sports sciences, 222 studies were found (Fig. 7.) and their distribution by country was shown (Fig. 8.). 23 studies Article and 4 review from 2024 were found (Fig. 9.) In this study, 19 study articles were analyzed.

When the studies are examined, it is seen that they are mostly done on team sports [45-49] and runners [50-54]. When we look at the use of

[45, 49, 51, 53-58] are the primary reasons for preference. In addition, it is observed that wearable technology is among the reasons for preference in preventing sports injuries. When the performance tracking of Paralympic athletes is evaluated, the point that wearable technology has reached is more clearly seen.

This technology is about to take its place among the indispensables in individual sports [58-60] and studies related to healthy living [61, 62]. The use of wearable technology also draws attention to determining the validity and reliability [47, 63] of tests and devices.

4. Conclusion

The rapid advancement of technology has enabled different disciplines to come together and produce new products.

The ever-growing wearable technology market continues to progress every day, attracting the attention of researchers and marketing professionals. In a field that is constantly updated, the continuity of research has also increased. The rapid advancement of technology provides a great deal of benefit. However, as it facilitates human life, it also brings some potentials. In the use of wearable technologies, it is very important to adopt these technologies, to use them effectively, to have sufficient knowledge and to evaluate the data obtained consciously.

Wearable technologies have opened the door to many exciting applications, leading to another technological revolution similar to the internet and mobile communication industries. They have been widely applied and preferred in industries such as electronics, fashion/textiles, education, health, defense, etc., which have a significant impact on world trade due to the convenience they provide. Wearable technologies have developed more and more every day and wearable technology products have become a part of everyday life. These developments are progressing to dizzying heights for both businesses and consumers. The underlying technology and logistics of wearables in healthcare are still in their infancy and more work is needed. As a result, more work needs to be done by physicians, programmers, and wearable device manufacturers to overcome logistical and practical barriers and ensure the seamless incorporation of wearables into the digital platforms of healthcare systems. In addition to the analysis of all this data, personal data security also stands before us as a very important security issue for wearable technological devices.

Considering the increasing technological developments, it is evaluated that the studies in this field will increase in parallel with this development and will make great contributions to the field of sports sciences.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest is declared by the authors. In addition, no financial support was received.

Author Contributions

Study Design, DSSU, NEA; Literature Search, DSSU, NEA; Data Collection, DSSU, NEA; Manuscript Preparation, DSSU, NEA; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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